

A novel electroorganic synthesis of some 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles at the platinum electrode

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Abstract : The electroorganic synthesis of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles from semicarbazone has been carried out at platinum electrode. This is an environmentally benign electroorganic reaction done under controlled potential electrolysis in an undivided cell. The non-aqueous solvent and a supporting electrolyte has been used for the electrolysis in the electrooxidation.

Keywords : Electrooxidation, controlled potential electrolysis, supporting electrolyte, oxadiazole, acylhydrazine, platinum electrode, green chemistry.

Introduction

Recent advances in the technology for the development of ecofriendly synthetic method has great importance and is the need of the hour¹⁻⁷. A multistep conventional synthesis produces considerable large amount of environmentally unfavourable wastes mainly due to a series of complex isolation procedure involving expensive and toxic solvents after each step.

The electrochemical cyclization has certain merits. These reactions do not require oxidizing chemicals and can be performed at room temperature. Application of electricity as a non conventional energy source for activation of reactants in suitable solvents has now gained popularity over the usual homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions. It provides chemical processes with special attributes, such as enhanced reaction rate, higher yield of pure products, better selectivity and several ecofriendly advantages.

A large number of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles has been reported to possess anti-microbial⁸⁻¹⁰, anti-fungal^{11,12}, anti-inflammatory¹³, hypotensive¹⁴, muscle relaxant¹⁵ and antimicrobial activity¹⁶ and the methods required to synthesise these molecules involve bromine, the handling of which is very dangerous and is environmentally hazardous.

Various chemical reactions such as oxidation^{17,18},

reduction¹⁹⁻²¹ and substitution²² have been carried out by the author. In the continuation of work an effort had been made as a trial method for the electrooxidation of semicarbazone **3** to prepare 1,3,4-oxadiazole **4** and was successful.

Results and discussion

Reported method of synthesis of oxadiazoles^{23,24} **4** include bromine oxidation of semicarbazide derivative and the cyclodesulfurisation of acylthiosemicarbazide derivative in solution using $I_2/NaOH$ or 1,3-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)²⁵⁻²⁸, as well as mercury(II) acetate $[Hg(OAc)_2]$ or yellow mercury(II) oxide HgO ^{29,30}. All these methods are usually carried out in different synthetic steps and every step requires great precautions.

Evans and co-workers³⁰ have reported a similar cyclized product by the chemical method, where 192 ($12R^1 \times 16R^2$) 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared by rapid parallel synthesis in efficient one-pot preparation using resin-bound reagents.

Our objective was to find out a new general ecofriendly

synthetic method for the preparation of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles in which the use of above said reagents could be minimised by amount and number both. Keeping these objectives in mind we have synthesized a large number of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles **4** by electroorganic cyclization of semicarbazone **3**. This electrochemical cyclization gives the oxadiazoles (Scheme 1) without requirement of any hazardous reagents. We have used a non aqueous solvent acetonitrile and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) as an electrolyte that can be handled very easily without major precautions.

Scheme 1. Electrochemical cyclization of semicarbazone for the synthesis of oxadiazoles **4**.

Mechanism :

It is evident from the CV studies that the process is one electron oxidation process. In the Scheme 1 conjugate base (**3a**) is more resonance stabilized than acid (**3**) and hence under reaction conditions acid (**3**) ionizes to give more stable conjugate base (**3a**). The elimination of hydride ion (H^-) in the last step followed by cyclization resulted in the formation of aromatic compound. Aromatic stabilization is the driving force behind the elimination of hydride ion. Greater the electron releasing nature of R^1 , easier will be the dropping of hydride ion (H^-) and easier will the formation of aromatic system.

The first step represents the deprotonation of **3** to form an anion (**3a**) which after one electron oxidation

evolves a free radical (**3b**). Subsequent second electron reduction from the resonanced form of free radical (**3c**) gives a diradical anion (**3d**). The coupling of carbon free radical with oxygen free radical completes the ring by forming a covalent bond. On losing a hydride anion in the last step, 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole (**4**) is obtained.

Fig. 1 presents the cyclic voltogram obtained from a 0.25 mM solution of LiClO_4 . The corresponding voltogram exhibits one anodic peak at 1446 V vs the reference electrode. This peak corresponds to the oxidation of semicarbazone to the product (**4j**).

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of **4j** at a glassy carbon electrode ($S = \pi \text{ mm}^2$) in 0.01 M LiClO_4 - AN, scan rate 2000 (v/s).

All the electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potential and completed in 3 to 5 h. The current potential data were recorded at the interval of 15 min which is depicted in Table 1.

Experimental

Reagents : The high purity chemicals acetonitrile (Merck), lithium perchlorate (Lobachem) and chloroform (Merck) were purchased from standard manufacturers. The water used was double distilled.

Preparation of reaction mixture :

For constant potential electrolysis a reaction mixture was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of substrate and supporting electrolyte in acetonitrile.

Preparation of reaction mixture for electrocyclic cyclization of semicarbazone : Semicarbazone **3** (1.0 g) was dissolved in acetonitrile (100 mL) and LiClO_4 (0.106 g) was dissolved in the above solution maintaining the strength of supporting electrolyte 0.001 M.

Table 1. Current-potential data of electroorganic synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles

Entry	R	Time (h)	Applied potential (V)	Current (A)	Yield in acetonitrile (%)	Yield in acetic acid (%)
4a	<i>p</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ -	3	1.44	0.12	80	88
4b	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	5	2.50	0.11	92	96
4c	<i>m</i> -(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄ -	4	2.50	0.07	81	86
4d	<i>o</i> -(OH)C ₆ H ₄ -	3	1.25	0.08	90	92
4e		4	2.00	0.05	68	74
4f	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	4	2.02	0.11	65	69
4g	C ₆ H ₅ -	5	2.35	0.09	77	81
4h	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ -	5	1.95	0.12	81	85
4i	CH ₃ -CH=CH-	3	1.80	0.09	84	92
4j	<i>o</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ -	4	1.43	0.07	81	87
4k	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -	3	2.23	0.06	78	86
4l	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	5	2.20	0.12	82	90

Electrolysis : Preparative scale constant potential electrolysis were performed at room temperature in 250 mL three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate (flattened sheet of dimension 1.0 cm × 0.5 cm) as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode¹⁷⁻²². Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. The current-potential data given in the table was recorded with the help of potential cum galvanostat. Approximately 4.5–6 F mol⁻¹ of electricity was passed for the electrolysis which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods.

All the electrolysis experiments were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potentials and were completed in 3 to 5 h. After which no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. All the products were solid and coloured and entirely different from the starting compound. The compounds were detected by chemical and spectral analysis.

Apart from acetonitrile these experiments were also performed in acetic acid and the products formed were extracted in the similar manner.

Extraction : The product was extracted from acetonitrile to chloroform by simple solvent extraction method³¹⁻³³. Oxadiazoles 4 were obtained in excellent purity and good yield after evaporation of chloroform. As depicted in the Table 1, it is observed that the yield in case of

acetic acid is about 5–10% higher than acetonitrile in almost similar conditions.

Spectral analysis :

IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000–400 cm⁻¹). NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz) FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield from TMS as internal reference.

2-Amino-5-(*p*-methoxy)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula C₉H₉N₃O₂, mol. wt. 191; IR (KBr) : 735–860 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2850 (aliphatic C-H), 3040 (Ar-C-H), 3336 cm⁻¹ (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 3.73 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 7.25–7.69 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 125.5–137 (Ar-C), 48.5 (-OCH₃) (Found : C, 55.94; H, 4.65; N, 21.84. Require : C, 56.54; H, 4.71; N, 21.97%).

2-Amino-5-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4b) : Orange colour needle, molecular formula C₈H₆N₃OCl, mol. wt. 195.5; IR (KBr) : 600–800 (Ar-Cl), 735–860 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 3055 (Ar-C-H), 3360 cm⁻¹ (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.00–7.15 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 125.5–137.7 (Ar-C)

(Found : C, 49.12; H, 3.02; N, 21.35; Cl, 18.10. Requires : C, 49.10; H, 3.06; N, 21.48; Cl, 18.15%).

2-Amino-5-(*m*-nitro)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4c) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula $C_8H_6N_4O_3$, mol. wt. 206; IR (KBr) : 690–810 (*o*-, *m*-disubstituted benzene), 1580 (Ar-NO₂), 3035 (ArC-H), 3341 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.25–7.69 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 123–135 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 46.10; H, 2.55; N, 26.80. Requires : C, 46.60; H, 2.91; N, 27.18%).

2-Amino-5-(*o*-hydroxy)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4d) : Brownish needle, molecular formula $C_8H_7N_3O_2$, mol. wt. 177; IR (KBr) : 735–860 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 1050 (OH), 3045 (ArC-H), 3350 (NH), 3640 cm^{-1} (phenolic); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.25–7.69 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 125.5–137.7 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 53.88; H, 3.85; N, 23.10. Requires : C, 54.23; H, 3.95; N, 23.73%).

2-Amino-5-furfuryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4e) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula $C_6H_6N_4O_2$, mol. wt. 166; IR (KBr) : 3060 (furan C-H), 3360 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.26 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 109.9–143 (Ar-C furan) (Found : C, 43.51; H, 3.59; N, 33.48. Requires : C, 43.37; H, 3.61; N, 33.73%).

2-Amino-5-(2-phenyl)ethenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4f) : Wine red colour, molecular formula $C_{10}H_9N_3O$, mol. wt. 187; IR (KBr) : 700–900 (aromatic), 1645 (C=C), 3045 (ArC-H), 3050 (=C-H), 3261 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.46–7.14 (5H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 125–128.5 (Ar-C), 14 (-CH=CH) (Found : C, 63.89; H, 4.70; N, 22.40. Requires : C, 64.17; H, 4.81; N, 22.45%).

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4g) : Wine red colour, molecular formula $C_8H_7N_3O$, mol. wt. 161; IR (KBr) : 750 (mono substituted benzene), 3045 (ArC-H), 3360 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.94–7.14 (5H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 125–128.5 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 59.50; H, 4.35; N, 26.03. Requires : C, 59.61; H, 4.34; N, 26.08%).

2-Amino-5-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethylamino)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4h) : Dark blackish needle, molecular formula $C_{10}H_{12}N_4O$, mol. wt. 204; IR (KBr) : 2855 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (ArC-H), 3170 (tert. amine), 3336 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.35 (6H, s, CH₃), 6.94–7.14 (5H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 13.7 (CH₃), 115–146 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 58.61; H, 5.77; N, 26.92. Requires : C, 58.82; H, 5.87; N, 27.45%).

2-Amino-5-crotonyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4i) : Brownish needle, molecular formula $C_5H_7N_3O$, mol. wt. 125; IR (KBr) : 1650 (C=C), 2868 (aliphatic C-H), 3055 (=C-H), 3261 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : 13.7 (aliphatic-C) (Found : C, 47.79; H, 5.65; N, 33.61. Requires : C, 48.00; H, 5.60; N, 33.60%).

2-Amino-5-(*o*-methoxy)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4j) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula $C_9H_9N_4O_2$, mol. wt. 205; IR (KBr) : 669.2–749.5 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 1544.4 (C=N), 2856.2 (O-CH₃), 2856 (aliphatic C-H), 2927 (Ar C-H), 3444 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.52–7.14 (8H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 128.4–129.5 (Ar-C), 46.7 (-OCH₃) (Found : C, 52.41; H, 4.43; N, 26.96. Requires : C, 52.68; H, 4.40; N, 27.31%).

2-Amino-5-(*o*-chloro)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4k) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula $C_8H_6N_3OCl$, mol. wt. 195.5; IR (KBr) : 700–900 (Ar-Cl), 735–860 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 3050 (ArC-H), 3360 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.94–7.04 (4H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 114–121 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 48.87; H, 3.02; N, 21.35; Cl, 18.10. Requires : C, 49.10; H, 3.06; N, 21.48; Cl, 18.15%).

2-Amino-5-(2,4-dinitro)phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4l) : Dark brownish needle, molecular formula $C_8H_5N_5O_5$, mol. wt. 251; IR (KBr) : 735–860 (*o*-, *p*-disubstituted benzene), 1570 (Ar-NO₂), 3045 (ArC-H), 3325 cm^{-1} (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.94–7.14 (3H, s, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 114–152 (Ar-C) (Found : C, 38.21; H, 2.01; N, 27.78. Requires : C, 38.24; H, 2.00; N, 27.89%).

Conclusion :

It is obvious from the above studies that the one pot

electrochemical synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives is an example of electrocyclization by electrooxidation of semicarbazone. It provides a good method for oxadiazole synthesis in good yields which is not so easy to achieve by chemical methods. In the present electrolytic method, electrolysis was carried out at room temperature and no hazardous chemicals were used. Hence the method is ecofriendly and a contribution to green chemistry.

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